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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

O‘ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BORASIDAGI ISHLAR

Isomiddinov Sherzod Sirojiddin o‘g‘li

*Mirzo Ulug‘bek nomidagi O‘zbekiston milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali
Iqtisodiyot va turizm kafedrasi o‘qituvchisi*

E-MAIL: sherzodisomiddinov1912@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda turizm sohasini rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, ularning ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy ta‘siri, hamda mamlakatning turistik salohiyatini oshirishga qaratilgan strategiyalar ko‘rib chiqiladi. O‘zbekistonning boy madaniy merosi va tarixiy obidalarini hisobga olgan holda, davlat dasturlari, xalqaro hamkorlik va infratuzilma rivoji kabi muhim omillar tahlil etiladi. Shuningdek, mavjud muammolar va kelajak istiqbollari, jumladan, ekoturizm va raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida turizm sohasini yanada takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari ham muhokama qilinadi. Maqola O‘zbekiston turizmining joriy holati va uning rivojlanish yo‘llarini aniqlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: O‘zbekiston, Turizm, Rivojlanish, Madaniy meros, Davlat dasturlari, Xalqaro hamkorlik, Infratuzilma, Ekoturizm, Raqamli texnologiyalar, Iqtisodiy ta‘sir.

Kirish

O‘zbekiston, o‘zining noyob tarixi, madaniyati va tabiiy go‘zalliklari bilan turizm sohasida katta salohiyatga ega. Mamlakatning qadimiy shaharlaridan biri bo‘lgan Samarqand, Buxoro va Xiva, dunyo miqyosida tan olingan obidalar sifatida tarixiy va madaniy turizmni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan dasturlar, muammolar va kelajak istiqbollari ko‘rib chiqiladi.

1. O‘zbekistonning turistik salohiyati

O‘zbekistonning turistik salohiyati juda keng. Bu yurt, ming yillik tarixga ega bo‘lib, ko‘plab tarixiy obidalarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Samarqanddagi Registon maydoni, Buxorodagi Ark, Xivadagi Ichan-Qal'a kabi joylar, turistlarni o‘ziga jalb etadi.

O‘zbekistonning geografik joylashuvi, uning o‘ziga xos tabiiy go‘zalliklari, tog‘lar va cho‘llar bilan ajralib turadi, bu esa ekoturizmni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlarini yaratadi.

2. Davlat siyosati va dasturlar

O‘zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha bir qator davlat dasturlari ishlab chiqilgan. 2018-yilda qabul qilingan “Turizmni rivojlantirishning 2019-2025 yillarga mo‘ljallangan dasturi” doirasida turizm sohasini yanada rivojlantirishga qaratilgan strategiyalar belgilandi. Ushbu dastur quyidagi maqsadlarni ko‘zda tutadi:

- Turistik infratuzilmani yaxshilash;
- Mahalliy va xalqaro turizmni rivojlantirish;
- Yangi xizmatlar va yo‘nalishlarni taklif qilish;
- O‘zbekistonni turizm markaziga aylantirish.

3. Xalqaro hamkorlik

O‘zbekiston turizm sohasida xalqaro hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga katta e‘tibor qaratmoqda. BMTning Turizm Tashkiloti va boshqa xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlik, mamlakatning turistik salohiyatini yanada oshirishda muhim omil bo‘lib xizmat qilmoqda. O‘zbekiston, shuningdek, xalqaro turizm ko‘rgazmalarida ishtirok etish orqali o‘z brendini shakllantirishga harakat qilmoqda.

4. Ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy ta’sir

Turizm sohasining rivojlanishi O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga ijobiy ta’sir ko‘rsatmoqda. Bu soha orqali mahalliy aholi uchun yangi ish o‘rinlari yaratilmoqda, shuningdek, turizm xizmatlari orqali hududiy rivojlanish qo‘llab-quvvatlanmoqda. Mamlakatda turizmdan olinadigan daromadlar ijtimoiy dasturlarga, infratuzilmani rivojlantirishga va ta’lim sohasiga sarflanmoqda.

5. Muammolar va qiyinchiliklar

O‘zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirishda bir qator muammolar mavjud. Infratuzilmaning yetarlicha rivojlanmasligi, xizmat ko‘rsatish sifatining pastligi, madaniy merosni saqlashdagi muammolar va marketing strategiyalarining yetarlicha samarali bo‘lmasligi — bu barcha omillar turizm sohasining rivojlanishiga to‘sqinlik qilmoqda.

6. Kelajak istiqbollari

O‘zbekistonning turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda bir qator istiqbollari mavjud. Ekoturizm va madaniy turizmni rivojlantirish, shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsion yechimlarni joriy etish orqali turizm sohasini takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari mavjud. Masalan, smart-turizm konseptini joriy etish, turistlarga yanada qulay va sifatli xizmatlar ko‘rsatishga imkon beradi.

Xulosa

O‘zbekistonda turizm sohasini rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar mamlakatning iqtisodiy o‘shishiga, madaniy merosini saqlab qolish va yangi imkoniyatlar yaratishga qaratilgan. Mamlakatning turizm salohiyatini yanada oshirish uchun infratuzilmani rivojlantirish, xalqaro hamkorlikni kuchaytirish va xizmat ko‘rsatish sifatini yaxshilash zarur. Kelajakda O‘zbekistonni xalqaro turizm xaritasida mustahkamlash imkoniyatlari mavjud bo‘lib, bu soha mamlakatni yanada rivojlantirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

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